

Consumer Satisfaction in Himalaya Products

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Introduction

India is very vast, consumers here are naturally scattered over a vast territory. As the country is also marked by great diversity in climate, religion, language, literacy-level, customs, lifestyle, economic status, etc., here the consumers present a complex group. The heterogeneity holds many implications for a marketer, especially for those going in for nation marketing.

On the one hand, India has the highest concentration of illiterates in the world and on the other hand, it has the second highest concentration of literates and the third largest pool of educated and technically trained manpower in the world.

Consumer

A consumer is a person or group of people, such as a household, who are the final user of product or services. The consumer's use is final in the sense that the product is usually not improved by the use.

An individual who buys products or service from for personal use and not for manufacture or resale. A consumer is someone who can decide whether or not to purchase an item at the store, and someone who can be influenced by marketing and advertisements. Any time someone goes to a store and purchase a toy, shirt, beverage or anything else, they are making that decision as a consumer.

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction refers to the extent to which customers happy are happy with the products and services provided by a business. Customer satisfaction levels can be measured using survey techniques and questionnaires.

Gaining the high level of customer's satisfaction is very important to the business because satisfied customers are most likely to be loyal and to make repeat orders and to use a wide range of service offered by a business.

Statement of the Problem

This research is aiming to find out the present consumer satisfaction with the Herbal products and the study with special

reference to HIMALAYA Products in Erode town. The research on consumer satisfaction helps to identify the consumer and to know the consumer's preference, choice, taste and other quality parameters by conducting through analysis and survey with vibrant statistical methods. This study will help to earn more knowledge about the market share for each brand and identify the influencing the consumer's preference to select a particular brand available in the market and to find out the reason why the consumers are switching over to other brands.

Importance of the Study

- Quality of the product.
- Price level.
- Delivery time.
- Excellent customer relationship.

Scope of Study

- Size of the present and potential market.
- Consumer needs want habits and behavior.
- Dealer wants and preferences.
- The geographic location of customers.
- Analysis of market demand.
- Analysis of various channels of distribution.
- Study the market changes and market conditions.

Objectives of the Study

- To study consumer satisfaction towards utilization of the HIMALAYA Products.
- To identify the opinion of the customer about HIMALAYA Products.
- To study the awareness of HIMALAYA Products.
- To identify the various factors influencing the customer to purchase of HIMALAYA Products.
- To study the problem faced by HIMALAYA Products and give suggestions based on the findings.

Area of the Study

The study is confined to DHARMAPURI District which comprises DHARMAPURI TOWN

Limitations of the Study

- This study only focused on DHARMAPURI Town. Therefore the findings of this research study can't extend to another area.
- For the economic and time constraints of the researches, the number of the respondent's way limit to 100 respondents.
- Only consumer viewpoints have been studied but the viewpoints of companies and distributors have not been studied.
- The accuracy depends up on the respondent's information.
- The research is based on primary data obtained from the consumer care is taken to present the result accurately.

Company Profile

The Himalaya Drug Company was founded in 1930 by Mr. M.Manal with a vision to bring Ayurveda to society in a contemporary form and to unravel the mystery behind the 5000 years old system of medicine. Himalaya's product range includes Pharmaceutical, Personal care, Baby care, Animal health and nutrition.

Research and Development

Research and development is "backbone" of the company. Himalaya's Research & Development facility is one of the biggest for an Ayurveda manufacturer, with about 200 multidisciplinary scientists.

The company believes that the key to growth lies in research validate by empirical evidence.

Brand Identity

The Himalaya brand has much in common with the mountain range from which it draws its name. For centuries, the Himalayas have been an icon of aspiration, of man's quest to unlock nature's secrets. They represent purity and lofty ideals.

International Presence

Today, Himalaya has offices in India, the US, Europe, the Middle East, South Africa and Southeast Asia. These offices manage and monitor the marketing and distribution of the Himalaya range of product to 89 countries.

Product Details

- Health Care
- Skin Care
- Hair Care
- Baby Care
- Animal Care

Research Methodology

Meaning

Research is common parlance refers to a search for knowledge. Research, simply put, is an endeavor to discover the answer to problems (intellectual and practical), through the application of scientific method to the knowable universe.

Definition

According to Robert Ross, research is essentially an investigation, a recording and an analysis of evidence to gain knowledge.

Sources on Data

- Primary data
- Secondary data.

Primary Data

The study is mainly based on primary data. First-hand information is collected and is used in the study. Convenience sampling method is adopted in selecting the respondents. Information has been collected from a sample of 100 respondents residing in Erode town.

Mode of the Collection of Primary Data

For the purpose of collecting data, a questionnaire was prepared administrated individually to the consumers. The information so collected has been edited for reliability and consistency and present in a master table.

Secondary Data

Necessary data have also been collected from sources like Books, Magazines and the Internet to make highest Himalaya Healthcare Ltd products.

Tools for Analysis

The analysis of data requires some closed related operations. Such as establishment of categories, the applications of those categories of raw data through coding tabulation and then drawing statistical information.

The collected data have been categorized and processed manually. The important tools used for analyze are as follows.

The data collected are analyzed by a simple percentage.

The simple ranking method is used to determine the reason for selecting Himalaya products.

Review of Literature

Brand performance is an abstract term and it is necessarily formed through more than one component. This study endeavors to put together the antecedents and components of brand preference and tries to create a comprehensive framework for the measurement of the brand preference in the Indian automobile context.

Suggestions

The following suggestions are given to improve the Himalaya Healthcare Ltd products;

1. As the respondents of customers above 40 years are minimum steps should be taken to encourage using the product.
2. The company has to introduce new flavors in tooth paste to attract the customer.
3. As the married and house wives customer are less in using the product some incentives should be given to them.
4. Try to cover small towns and village to attract the new customers.
5. The company has the minimum number of respondents know about the product through advertisement more advertisement should be given to the Himalaya health care ltd products.
6. As the company introduces the new pack of 250gms and 500gms.
7. To distribute the maximum number of the free sample.

Conclusion

Indian manufactures and retailers of Himalaya products bear in the mind that there is a rural market which is yet to be tapped fully hence step be taken by manufactures and rural market.

Efforts should be taken to improve the quality of the product on the reasonable price. Earning profit is possible only through the consumer's satisfaction.

If the Himalaya manufacture and its marketers have executed these suggestions, the desired result can be achieved in future.

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